

Sorption of Aliphatic Normal Alcohols of Cobalt Molybdate at 35°

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A series of sorption-desorption studies, at 35°, of methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, *n*-propyl alcohol and *n*-butyl alcohol vapours have been carried out on cobalt molybdate, activated at different temperatures, employing the quartz fibre spring technique. A permanent hysteresis loop is exhibited in each system. The hysteresis effect increases as the molecular weight of the sorbate increases. The sorptive capacity of cobalt molybdate shows the following trend in binding these vapours: methyl alcohol > ethyl alcohol > *n*-propyl alcohol > *n*-butyl alcohol. Time-adsorption curves constructed for the polar sorbate, show that the rate of adsorption follows the order: methyl alcohol > ethyl alcohol \approx *n*-propyl alcohol \approx *n*-butyl alcohol. The results have been explained in the light of 'Cavity theory' of hysteresis. A reasonably good fit for the BET equation has been obtained for all the systems. Specific surface area of the cobalt molybdate activated at 250°, 450° and 550°, for the four sorbates and the number of molecules in the monolayers have also been calculated. Pore structure was determined by applying the Kelvin equation.

NOW-a-days cobalt molybdate has become of great industrial applications as catalyst in oxidation of organic compounds. Number of review articles^{1, 2} dealing with the heterogeneous catalytic oxidation of hydrocarbon over cobalt molybdate, have been published in the recent years. Margolis¹ stressed the importance of the electron work function, whilst Sampson² qualitatively classified catalysts according to the type of semiconductivity present. The use of cobalt molybdate in the oxidation of butenes to maleic anhydride has been investigated by Sadykhova³, Aviestov⁴ and Bountiy⁵. Authors⁶ have already reported the heterogeneous vapour phase catalytic oxidation of toluene over supported cobalt molybdate catalysts.

In the present paper we report a series of sorption-desorption isotherms at 35° of normal aliphatic alcohols on cobalt molybdate, activated at different temperatures. Hysteresis has been explained in the light of the cavity theory.

Experimental

All the sorbate used were dried and distilled at their boiling points.

Method of the preparation of cobalt molybdate :

22.1 gm sodium molybdate dissolved in water was added drop by drop with constant stirring to 26.58 gm cobalt nitrate dissolved in water. The resulting mixture was evaporated on a water bath and the solid was washed with warm distilled water

till free of sodium ions (tested with zinc uranyl-acetate) and dried. This was finally heated in a furnace at 150° in presence of air, sieved to get -18+24 Tyler mesh size fractions and activated at 250°, 450° and 550° in presence of air. The cobalt molybdate occurs in two modifications that transform at above 420° and shows variable activity^{1, 4}. The same has been shown by the authors in their earlier paper⁶ also. The reason for the choice of activation temperature 250° as the lowest was that the adsorbed gases on the catalysts (Co₂, N₂, sulphides, water vapours) could only be removed completely at above 200°.

The quartz fibre spring technique was employed in the present investigations. The adsorbent was evacuated for 8-10 hr in adsorption apparatus before starting a sorption-desorption cycle. The adsorption apparatus was kept inside an air thermostat of the type constructed by Vernon⁷. The temperature of the thermostat was kept at 35° ± 0.1° by means of toluene regulator in conjunction with an electronic relay. The reason for the choice of 35° as the experimental temperature was that generally the physical adsorption takes place at temperatures at which liquefaction would occur and the temperature will be below the boiling points of the adsorbates. The springs of sensitivities ranging from 18.27 to 24.04 cm/g load were used. An Edwards high-vacuum pump which produces a pressure of 10⁻² mm was used. The manometer tube had a bore diameter of 1.2 cm. The mercury used in the manometer was purified by first passing it through a 10% nitric acid column, then distilling

Fig. 1. Sorption and desorption on cobalt molybdate, activated at 250°, of *n*-aliphatic alcohols at 35°.

1—methyl alcohol, 2—ethyl alcohol
3—*n*-propyl alcohol, 4—*n*-butyl alcohol
×—adsorption curve, ○—desorption curve.

Fig. 2. Sorption and desorption on cobalt molybdate, activated at 450°, of *n*-aliphatic alcohols at 35°.

1—methyl alcohol, 2—ethyl alcohol,
3—*n*-propyl alcohol, 4—*n*-butyl alcohol
×—adsorption curve, ○—desorption curve.

in air, and finally distilling in vacuum. A cathometer reading correct to within 10^{-2} mm was employed for measuring the length of the spring. By exposing the evacuated adsorbent to methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohol, at 35°, at their saturation pressures, the extent of sorption with time was measured.

Results and Discussion

In all the cases the hysteresis loop in permanent and has been reproduced up to the 4th cycle of sorption and desorption. The permanent and reproducible hysteresis loops obtained with the two samples activated at 250° and 450° are shown in Figs. 1, 2 respectively to facilitate a comparative study. In these figures the isotherms are presented by plotting the volume of sorbate (cc) taken per 100 g of cobalt molybdate against the relative vapour pressure. The amount of normal aliphatic alcohol taken up by cobalt molybdate, heated at 250°, 450° and 550°, at saturation pressure in the 1st cycles are : methyl alcohol 30, 34 and 23 cc, ethyl alcohol 27, 30 and 31 cc, *n*-propyl alcohol 20, 24 and 18 cc and *n*-butyl alcohol is 16, 15 and 14 cc respectively.

Time-adsorption curves: The time adsorption curves for the adsorption of methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohol vapours at 35°, on cobalt molybdate heated at 250°, are given in Fig. 3. The

Fig. 3. Time—adsorption curves for *n*-aliphatic alcohols at their saturation pressures, at 35°, on cobalt molybdate activated at 250°.

1—methyl alcohol, 2—ethyl alcohol,
3—*n*-propyl alcohol, 4—*n*-butyl alcohol.

rate curves show that, under similar experimental conditions, methyl alcohol is adsorbed on cobalt molybdate much faster than either ethyl, *n*-propyl or *n*-butyl alcohols. The time required for the attainment of the equilibrium is about 3 hr, 6 hr, 6 hr and 6½ hrs for methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohol respectively.

The isotherms of methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohols have clearly defined 'knees'. The size of the hysteresis loop shows the following trend: *n*-butyl > *n*-propyl > ethyl > methyl alcohol. The permanent and reproducible hysteresis obtained with polar sorbates can be explained in the light of 'ink bottle' or 'cavity theory'⁸ of hysteresis. The 'cavity theory' postulates that sorption-desorption hysteresis is due to the entrapping of liquid sorbates by cavities with constricted necks. With the larger sorbate molecules, a greater entrapping effect results. The molecular volume increases in the order methyl alcohol 42.74 cc, ethyl alcohol 62.28 cc, *n*-propyl alcohol 78.73 cc and *n*-butyl alcohol 95.50 cc, likewise the entrapping effect also increases, giving wider hysteresis loops (Figs. 1 and 2).

Further for the polar sorbates, the molecular volume seems to be the main factor upon which the extent of sorption depends. The effect is exhibited particularly by the isotherms of four alcohols. These alcohols have essentially the polarity methyl alcohol 1.70, ethyl alcohol 1.69D, *n*-propyl alcohol 1.68D and *n*-butyl alcohol 1.66D, so the decrease in the extent of sorption may be due to increase in molecular size and decrease in dipole moment. When the temperature of activation of cobalt molybdate is raised from 250° to 450° the sorption values at saturation pressure of methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohols have appreciably increased. Further increase in temperature to 550°, does not show any remarkable change in adsorption.

Application of BET equation :

The sorption isotherms of the four aliphatic alcohols on cobalt molybdate, activated at 250°, 450° and

550°, have clearly defined knees followed by linear portion. According to BET theory⁹ the 'knee' signifies the transition from monomolecular to multimolecular sorption. The BET equation has been applied to the isotherms of aliphatic alcohols by plotting $P/X(P_s - P)$ against P/P_s and the BET plots shown in Figs. 4a (250°) and 4b (450°), are straight lines. From the slope and intercept of the lines the monolayer capacities X_m , have been calculated. Alternatively the values of monolayer capacities X_B can also be read out directly from the isotherms with reasonable accuracy¹⁰. The isotherms of all the alcohols with the two samples display long straight portion after the knee. This feature is not strictly compatible with the BET equation which yields an inflection point in 'S' type isotherm. The point (B) at which linear portion begins indicates the completion of the monolayer. The sorption at point B is the monolayer capacity X_B . The values of monolayer capacities X_m and X_B , for the four sorbents and the relative vapour pressure at which the monolayers are fully formed are presented in Table 1. The agreement is good between the values of X_B and X_m .

The total number of methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohol molecules (N_o), contained in the monolayer of the surface of 1 g of cobalt molybdate have also been calculated, and the values are reported in Table 1.

Specific surface :

From the monolayer capacity X_m , the specific area of the surface (S) of the sorbent (activated at 250°, 450° and 550°), and the molecular diameter $D_{spherical}$ was calculated by the standard equations^{11,12}.

Fig. 4. BET plots for the sorption of aliphatic normal alcohols on cobalt molybdate.
 4a. Activated at 250°, 4b. Activated at 450°,
 1—MeOH, 2—EtOH, 3—*n*-PrOH, 4—*n*-BuOH.

TABLE 1—MONOLAYER CAPACITIES X_m AND X_B IN g PER g OF SORPTION, NUMBER OF ALCOHOL MOLECULES (N_o) CONTAINED IN THE MONOLAYER ON THE SURFACE OF 1 g OF COBALT MOLYBDATE AND THE CORRESPONDING RELATIVE VAPOUR PRESSURE

	Activated at 250°				Activated at 450°				Activated at 550°			
	X_m	X_B ($\times 10^{30}$)	N_o	P/P_o	X_m	X_B ($\times 10^{30}$)	N_o	P/P_o	X_m	X_B ($\times 10^{30}$)	N_o	P/P_o
MeOH	.0219	.022	4.13	.05	.0244	.024	4.59	.08	.024	.025	4.55	.082
EtOH	.0300	.030	3.92	.05	.0346	.035	4.58	.09	.032	.033	4.22	.085
<i>n</i> -PrOH	.0385	.039	3.86	.05	.0431	.043	4.32	.09	.040	.040	4.09	.090
<i>n</i> -BuOH	.0480	.048	3.90	.11	.0527	.052	4.28	.11	.050	.052	4.09	.120

The specific surface area of cobalt molybdate activated at 250°, 450° and 550° are shown in Table 2. The molecular diameter $D_{\text{spherical}}$ is

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC SURFACE OF COBALT MOLYBDATE CONSIDERING ALCOHOL MOLECULES AS SPHERES

	Molecular Cross-section in Å^2	Specific Surface in m^2/g of Cobalt molybdate		
		Activated at 250°	Activated at 450°	Activated at 550°
CH_3OH	21.20	87.62	97.41	96.56
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$	27.00	106.00	116.94	114.20
<i>n</i> - $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$	31.40	121.29	135.90	128.53
<i>n</i> - $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH}$	36.00	140.57	154.33	147.30

assumed for calculating the molecular cross-section. In all the samples the values of specific surface, goes on increasing from methyl to *n*-butyl alcohol. This is due to the incorrectness of assuming the four aliphatic alcohol molecules as spheres. Actually the aliphatic alcohol molecules are linear in shape increasing in length from methyl alcohol to ethyl alcohol, *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohol. It is not strictly correct to assume the cubical or spherical shape of the molecules. The linear adsorbed molecule can be held on the surface either perpendicular or parallel to the surface. Assuming that the alcohol molecule is a rectangular bar, it is necessary to calculate the cross-section area of the rod and also the area of one of the four sides along the length of the rod. The thickness of the hydrocarbon chain is 4.55 Å. Therefore the thickness

of all the four alcohols is assumed to be the same. From the volume of the molecules D^3 and its thickness 4.55 Å, the length of the linear molecules are also calculated. The area of the end and the side along the length of the linear molecule are also calculated and are shown in Table 3. The specific surface areas calculated by assuming both the modes of sorption have also been shown in the Table 3.

The following interesting conclusions emerge from the results of Table 3. In all the samples, heated at 250°, 450° and 550°, the values of specific surface obtained for the alcohols are practically the same if oriented sorption perpendicular to the surface of the linear alcohol molecules is assumed. If oriented sorption parallel to surface is assumed, the values of the specific surface goes on increasing from methyl to *n*-butyl alcohol. Therefore, it follows that sorption of the four aliphatic normal alcohols in the monolayers on the surface of cobalt molybdate, activated at 250°, 450° and 550° are of the oriented type perpendicular to surface.

Secondly, for this oriented type of sorption perpendicular to surface, the specific surface values obtained, of the cobalt molybdate activated at 450°, are higher than those of cobalt molybdate activated at 250° and 550°.

Pore size distribution :

According to the cavity theory of hysteresis, the desorption curve of hysteresis loop indicates the

TABLE 3—SPECIFIC SURFACE OF COBALT MOLYBDATE CONSIDERING ALCOHOL MOLECULES AS LINEAR

Diameter in Å	Length of the molecule in Å	Cross- section in Å^2	Area of side in Å^2	Specific Surface in m^2/g of Cobalt molybdate						
				Activated at 250°		Activated at 450°		Activated at 550°		
				Molecules perpendi- cular to surface	Molecules parallel to surface	Molecules perpendi- cular to surface	Molecules parallel to surface	Molecules perpendi- cular to surface	Molecules parallel to surface	
CH_3OH	4.6	4.7	20.7	21.4	85.5	88.4	95.0	98.3	94.3	97.4
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$	5.2	6.8	20.7	30.9	81.3	121.3	98.8	140.1	87.5	130.6
<i>n</i> - $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$	5.6	8.5	20.7	38.5	79.9	148.7	89.6	166.6	84.7	157.6
<i>n</i> - $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH}$	6.0	10.4	20.7	47.5	84.7	185.5	88.7	203.6	84.7	194.4

neck radius and sorption curve and the body radius of the cavity. The predominant neck and body radii of cavities are obtained from the mid points of the steep parts of desorption and sorption curves. The isotherm of methyl alcohol has been employed. Body and neck radii have been calculated by applying the Kelvin equation¹⁸.

The pore size distribution curve obtained with methyl alcohol adsorbed on cobalt molybdate activated at 250° is shown in Fig. 5. The predominant neck and body radii of cavities obtained for cobalt molybdate activated at 250°, 450° and 550°, with methyl alcohol are shown in Table 4. The results show that the values of smallest neck radii, the predominant cavity body and neck radii remain almost the same on heating cobalt molybdate from 250° to 550°. Higher temperature has not changed markedly the porous structure of cobalt molybdate.

Fig. 5. Pore size distribution in cobalt molybdate activated at 250°, for sorption isotherm-x, Desorption isotherm-o.

TABLE 4—PORE SIZE DISTRIBUTION IN Å IN COBALT MOLYBDATE

	Smallest neck radius	Predominant neck radius	Predominant neck radius
Cobalt molybdate Activated at 250°	3.40	3.60	4.54
Cobalt molybdate Activated at 450°	3.60	4.00	5.05
Cobalt molybdate Activated at 550°	3.40	3.70	4.72

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